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AKRAMOV Davron Rixsitullayevich

Lecturer of Business Law and Economics

At International School of Finance and Technology

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STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT ANALYSIS

ANNOTATION

In the conditions of tough competition and rapidly changing situation, companies should not only focus on the internal state of affairs, but also develop a long-term strategy of behavior that would allow them to keep up with the changes occurring in their environment. In the past, many companies could function successfully, paying attention mainly to daily work, to internal problems associated with increasing the efficiency of resource use in current activities. Now, although the task of rational use of potential in current activities is not removed, it is extremely important to implement such management that ensures the adaptation of the company to rapidly changing business conditions. Acceleration of changes in the environment, the emergence of new demands and changes in the consumer's position, increased competition for resources, internationalization of business, the emergence of new unexpected opportunities for business opened up by the achievements of science and technology, the development of information networks that make it possible to disseminate and receive information at lightning speed, the wide availability of modern technologies, the change in the role of human resources, as well as a number of other reasons have led to a sharp increase in the importance of strategic management.

Key words: strategy, management, analysis, strategic management, strategic management analysis, potential, environment, competition.

СТРАТЕГИК БОШҚАРУВ ТАҲЛИЛИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Қаттиқ рақобат ва тез ўзгаришчан вазият шароитида компаниялар нафақат ички ишларга ётибор қаратишлари, балки атроф-муҳитдаги ўзгаришларни кузатиб боришга имкон берадиган узок муддатли хатти-ҳаракатлар стратегиясини ишлаб чиқишлари керак. Илгари, кўплаб компаниялар асосан кундалик ишларга, жорий фаолиятда ресурслардан фойдаланиш самарадорлигини ошириш билан боғлиқ ички муаммоларга ётибор бериб, муваффақиятли ишлаши мумкин еди. Ёнди, ҳозирги фаолиятда потенциалдан оқилона фойдаланиш вазифаси олиб ташланмаса ҳам, компаниянинг тез ўзгаришчан бизнес шароитларига мослашишини таъминлайдиган бундай бошқарувни амалга ошириш жуда муҳимдир. Атроф-муҳитдаги ўзгаришларнинг тезлашиши, истеъмолчининг позициясида янги талаблар ва ўзгаришларнинг пайдо бўлиши, ресурслар учун рақобатнинг кучайиши, бизнесни халқаролаштириш, фан ва техника ютуқлари билан очилган бизнес учун янги кутилмаган имкониятларнинг пайдо бўлиши, ахборот тармоқларини ривожлантириш. тарқатиш ва қабул қилишга имкон берадиган яшин тезлигида маълумот, замонавий технологияларнинг кенг мавжудлиги, инсон ресурслари ролининг ўзгариши, шунингдек, бошқа бир қатор сабаблар стратегик менежментнинг аҳамиятини кескин оширишга олиб келди.

Калит сўзлар: стратегик, бошқарув, таҳлил, стратегик бошқарув, стратегик бошқарув таҳлили, потенциал, атроф-муҳит, рақобат.

СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКИЙ УПРАВЛЕНЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В условиях жесткой конкуренции и быстро меняющейся ситуации компаниям следует не только сосредоточиться на внутренней работе, но и разработать долгосрочные стратегии поведения, позволяющие им отслеживать изменения в окружающей среде. Раньше многие компании могли успешно работать, сосредоточившись в основном на повседневной деятельности, внутренних проблемах, связанных с повышением эффективности использования ресурсов в текущей деятельности. В настоящее время, хотя задача рационального использования потенциала в текущей деятельности не снята, очень важно осуществлять такое управление, которое обеспечивает адаптацию компании к быстро меняющимся условиям ведения бизнеса. Ускорение изменений в окружающей среде, появление новых требований и изменение позиции потребителя, усиление конкуренции за ресурсы, интернационализация бизнеса, появление новых неожиданных возможностей для бизнеса, открываемых достижениями науки и техники, развитие информационных сетей, молниеносное получение информации, широкая доступность современных технологий, изменение роли человеческих ресурсов, а также ряд других причин, позволяющих распространять и внедрять их, привели к резкому повышению значимости стратегического управления.

Ключевые слова: стратегия, менеджмент, анализ, стратегическое управление, стратегический управленческий анализ, потенциал, окружающая среда, конкуренция.

I. Introduction

In the conditions of tough competition and rapidly changing situation, companies should not only focus on the internal state of affairs, but also develop a long-term strategy of behavior that would allow them to keep up with the changes occurring in their environment. In the past, many companies could function successfully, paying attention mainly to daily work, to internal problems associated with increasing the efficiency of resource use in current activities.

Now, although the task of rational use of potential in current activities is not removed, it is extremely important to implement such management that ensures the adaptation of the company to rapidly changing business conditions.

Acceleration of changes in the environment, the emergence of new demands and changes in the consumer's position, increased competition for resources, internationalization of business, the emergence of new unexpected opportunities for business opened up by the achievements of science and technology, the development of information networks that make it possible to disseminate and receive information at lightning speed, the wide availability of modern technologies, the change in the role of human resources, as well as a number of other reasons have led to a sharp increase in the importance of strategic management.

There is no single strategy for all companies, just as there is no single universal strategic management. Each company is unique in its own way, therefore the process of developing a strategy for each company is unique, since it depends on the company's position in the market, the dynamics of its development, its potential, the behavior of competitors, the characteristics of the goods it produces or the services it provides, the state of the economy, the cultural environment and many other factors.

At the same time, there are some fundamental points that allow us to talk about some generalized principles for developing a behavior strategy and implementing strategic management. In this paper, we will consider three extremely important issues of strategic management: how to understand strategic management, what is its essence and content; what is a company's strategy and how is it developed; the strategic line of orientation of the company to the consumer and the role of marketing in implementing this line of behavior.

II. General characteristics of strategic management:

2.1 The essence of strategic management.

The term "strategic management" was introduced into circulation at the turn of the 60-70s in order to reflect the difference between management carried out at the highest level and current management at the production level. The need to make such a distinction was caused primarily by changes in the conditions of business.

The leading idea reflecting the essence of the transition to strategic management from operational management was the idea of the need to shift the focus of top management to the environment in order to respond appropriately and promptly to the changes occurring in it, and to respond promptly to the challenge posed by the external environment.

Strategic management can be defined as such management of an organization that relies on human potential as the foundation of the organization, orients production activities to consumer demands, implements flexible regulation and timely changes in the organization that respond to the challenge from the environment and allow achieving competitive advantages, which together allows the organization to survive and achieve its goal in the long term.

Although strategic management is the most important factor for successful survival in an increasingly complex competitive environment, one can nevertheless constantly observe a lack of strategy in the actions of organizations, which often leads to their defeat in the market struggle. The lack of strategic management manifests itself primarily in the following two forms:

First, organizations plan their activities based on the fact that the environment will either not change at all, or will not undergo qualitative changes in it. In non-strategic management, a plan of specific actions is drawn up both in the present and in the future, a priori based on the fact that the final state is clearly known and that the environment will not actually change. Drawing up long-term plans that prescribe what and when to do and searching for solutions for many years to come in the initial period, the desire to build "for centuries" or to acquire "for many years" - all these are signs of non-strategic management.

A long-term vision is a very important component of management. However, this should in no way mean extrapolating existing practices and the existing state of the environment for many years to come. In the case of strategic management, at any given moment, it is recorded what the organization should do at the present time in order to achieve the desired goals in the future, based on the fact that the environment and conditions of the organization's life will change, i.e., in strategic management, as it were, a view is taken from the future to the present.

The actions of the organization at the present time are determined and carried out, providing it with a certain future, and a plan or description of what the organization should do in the future is not developed. At the same time, it is characteristic of strategic management that not only the desired future state of the organization is recorded, but this is also the most important task of strategic management, the ability to respond to changes in the environment is developed, allowing the desired goals to be achieved in the future. Secondly, in non-strategic management, the development of an action program begins with an analysis of the internal capabilities and resources of the organization. With this approach, all that the organization can determine on the basis of an analysis of its internal capabilities is how much product it can produce and what costs it can incur. The volume of production and the amount of costs do not answer the question of how much the product created by the company will be accepted by the market - what quantity will be bought and at what price, the market will determine.

Along with obvious advantages, strategic management has a number of disadvantages and limitations in its use, which indicate that this type of management, as well as all others, does not have universal application in any situation to solve any problems.

Firstly, strategic management, by its nature, does not give, and cannot give an accurate and detailed picture of the future.

The desired future state of the organization formed in strategic management is not a detailed description of its internal and external position, but rather a qualitative wish for what state the organization should be in in the future, what position it should occupy in the market and in business, what organizational culture it should have, what business groups it should be a part of, etc. At the same time, all this together should be what will determine whether the organization will survive or not in the future in the competitive struggle.

Secondly, strategic management cannot be reduced to a set of routine procedures and schemes. It does not have a descriptive theory that prescribes what and how to do when solving certain problems or in specific situations. Strategic management is rather a certain philosophy or ideology of business and management. Each individual manager understands and implements it largely in his own way. Of course, there are a number of recommendations, rules and logical schemes for analyzing problems and choosing a strategy, as well as implementing strategic planning and practical implementation of strategy.

However, in general, strategic management is a symbiosis of intuition and the art of top management to lead the organization to strategic goals, high professionalism and creativity of employees, ensuring the connection of the organization with the environment, updating the organization and its products, as well as the implementation of current plans and, finally, the active involvement of all employees in the implementation of the organization's tasks, in the search for the best ways to achieve its goals. Thirdly, enormous efforts and large expenditures of time and resources are required for the strategic management process to begin to be implemented in the organization. It is necessary to create and implement strategic planning, which is fundamentally different from the development of long-term plans that are mandatory for implementation under any conditions. A strategic plan must be flexible, it must respond to changes inside and outside the organization, and this requires a lot of effort and great expense.

It is also necessary to create services that monitor the environment and include the organization in the environment. Marketing, public relations, etc. services acquire exceptional importance and require significant additional costs. Fourth, the negative consequences of errors in strategic foresight are sharply increased. In conditions when completely new products are created in a short time, when investment directions change dramatically in a short time, when new business opportunities suddenly arise and opportunities that have existed for many years disappear before our eyes, the price of paying for incorrect foresight and, accordingly, for errors in strategic choice often becomes fatal for the organization. The consequences of an incorrect forecast are especially tragic for organizations that are pursuing an uncontested path of functioning or implementing a strategy that is not amenable to fundamental adjustment.

Fifthly, when implementing strategic management, the main emphasis is often placed on strategic planning. In fact, the most important component of strategic management is the implementation of the strategic plan. This primarily involves creating an organizational culture that allows for the implementation of the strategy, creating motivation and labor organization systems, creating a certain flexibility in the organization, etc. At the same time, with strategic management, the implementation process has an active feedback effect on planning, which further enhances the importance of the implementation phase. Therefore, an organization, in principle, will not be able to move to strategic management if it has created, even a very good, strategic planning subsystem and at the same time there are no prerequisites or opportunities for creating a strategic implementation subsystem.

2.2 Strategic Management System.

Strategic management can be viewed as a dynamic set of five interrelated management processes. These processes logically follow from one another. However, there is a stable feedback loop and, accordingly, a feedback effect of each process on the others and on their entire set. This is an important feature of the strategic management system. The structure of strategic management is schematically shown in Fig. 1.

Environmental analysis is usually considered the initial process of strategic management, as it provides the basis for determining the mission and goals of the company and for developing behavior strategies that allow the company to fulfill the mission and achieve its goals. Environmental analysis involves studying its three parts:

- 1) the macroenvironment;
- 2) the immediate environment;
- 3) the internal environment.

Macroenvironment analysis includes studying the influence of such environmental components as: the state of the economy; legal regulation and management; political processes; the natural environment and resources; the social and cultural components of society; scientific, technical and technological development of society; infrastructure, etc.

The immediate environment is analyzed by the following main components: customers; suppliers; competitors; labor market.

Internal environment analysis reveals the internal capabilities and potential that a company can count on in the competitive struggle in the process of achieving its goals, and also allows for a more accurate formulation of the mission and a better understanding of the organization's goals. It is extremely important to always remember that the organization not only produces products for the environment, but also ensures the existence of its members, providing them with work, the opportunity to participate in profits, creating social conditions for them, etc.

The internal environment is analyzed in the following areas:

- the company's personnel, their potential, qualifications, interests, etc.;
- management organization;
- production, including organizational, operational and technical and technological characteristics, scientific research and development;
- company finances;
- marketing;
- organizational culture.

Definition of mission and goals, considered as one of the processes of strategic management, consists of three subprocesses, each of which requires a lot of and extremely responsible work. The first subprocess consists of defining the company's mission, which in a concentrated form expresses the meaning of the company's existence, its purpose. Next comes the subprocess of defining long-term goals. This part of strategic management is completed by the subprocess of defining short-term goals.

Definition of the company's mission and goals leads to the fact that it becomes clear why the company functions and what it strives for. And knowing this, you can more accurately choose a behavior strategy. After the mission and goals are defined, the stage of analysis and selection of strategy begins. This process is rightfully considered the core of strategic management. With the help of special techniques, the organization determines how it will achieve its goals and implement its mission. Implementation of the strategy is a critical process, since it is this process, in the case of successful implementation, that leads the company to achieve its goals. Very often there are cases when companies are unable to implement the chosen strategy. This happens either because the analysis was conducted incorrectly and incorrect conclusions were made, or because unexpected changes occurred in the external environment.

However, the strategy is often not implemented because management cannot properly involve the company's existing potential for implementing the strategy. This is especially true for the use of labor potential.

Evaluation and control of strategy implementation is the logical last process carried out in strategic management. This process ensures stable feedback between how the process of achieving goals is going and the organization's goals themselves.

The main tasks of any control are the following:

1) determining what and by what indicators to check;

2) assessing the state of the controlled object in accordance with accepted standards, regulations or other benchmarks;

3) identifying the causes of deviations, if any are revealed as a result of the assessment;

4) making adjustments, if necessary and possible. In the case of monitoring the implementation of strategies, these tasks acquire a very specific nature, due to the fact that strategic control is aimed at finding out to what extent the implementation of strategies leads to the achievement of the company's goals. This fundamentally distinguishes strategic control from management or operational control, since it is not interested in the correctness of the implementation of the strategic plan, the correctness of the strategy implementation, or the correctness of the execution of individual works, functions, and operations. Strategic control is focused on whether it is possible to further implement the adopted strategies and whether their implementation will lead to the achievement of the set goals. Adjustment based on the results of strategic control may concern both the strategies and the goals of the company.

III. Environmental Analysis.

Any organization is located and functions in an environment. Each action of all organizations without exception is possible only if the environment allows its implementation. The internal environment of an organization is the source of its life force. It contains the potential that enables the organization to function, and therefore, to exist and survive in a certain period of time. But the internal environment can also be a source of problems and even the death of the organization if it does not ensure the necessary functioning of the organization.

The external environment is a source that feeds the organization with resources necessary to maintain its internal potential at the proper level. The organization is in a state of constant exchange with the external environment, thereby ensuring its own survival. But the resources of the external environment are not unlimited. And many other organizations in the same environment lay claim to them. Therefore, there is always a possibility that the organization will not be able to obtain the necessary resources from the external environment. This can weaken its potential and lead to many negative consequences for the organization. The task of strategic management is to ensure such interaction of the organization with the environment that would allow it to maintain its potential at the level necessary to achieve its goals, and thus would give it the opportunity to survive in the long term. In order to determine the strategy of the organization's behavior and implement this strategy, management must have an in-depth understanding of both the internal environment of the organization, its potential and development trends, and the external environment, its development trends and the place occupied by the organization in it. At the same time, both the internal environment and the external environment are studied by strategic management primarily in order to reveal those threats and opportunities that the organization must take into account when determining its goals and achieving them [1].

3.1 Analysis of the external environment.

The external environment in strategic management is considered as a combination of two relatively independent subsystems: the macroenvironment and the immediate environment.

The macroenvironment creates the general conditions of the environment in which the organization is located. In most cases, the macroenvironment is not specific to a particular organization. However, the degree of influence of the state of the macroenvironment on different organizations varies. This is due to both differences in the areas of activity of organizations and differences in the internal potential of organizations.

The study of the economic component of the macroenvironment allows us to understand how resources are formed and distributed. It involves the analysis of such characteristics as the size of the gross national product, the rate of inflation, the unemployment rate, the interest rate, labor productivity, tax rates, the balance of payments, the accumulation rate, etc.

When studying the economic component, it is important to pay attention to such factors as the general level of economic development, extracted natural resources, climate, the type and level of development of competitive relations, the structure of the population, the level of education of the workforce and the number of wages. Analysis of legal regulation, which involves studying laws and other regulations establishing legal norms and frameworks for relations, enables an organization to determine for itself the permissible boundaries of actions in relations with other legal entities and acceptable methods of defending its interests. The study of legal regulation should not be limited to studying the content of legal acts. It is important to pay attention to such aspects of the legal environment as the effectiveness of the legal system, established traditions in this area and the procedural side of the practical implementation of legislation. The political component of the macroenvironment should be studied primarily in order to have a clear idea of the intentions of government bodies regarding the development of society and the means by which the state intends to implement its policy.

The study of the political component should focus on finding out what programs various party structures are trying to implement, what lobbying groups exist in government bodies, what attitude the government has towards various sectors of the economy and regions of the country, what changes in legislation and legal regulation are possible as a result of the adoption of new laws and new norms regulating economic processes. It is important to understand such basic characteristics of the political subsystem as: what political ideology determines the government's policy, how stable the government is, how capable it is of implementing its policy, what is the degree of general discontent and how strong are the opposition political structures in order to use this discontent to seize power.

The study of the social component of the macroenvironment is aimed at understanding the influence of such social phenomena and processes on business as: people's attitudes to work and quality of life; customs and beliefs existing in society; values shared by people; demographic structures of society, population growth, level of education, mobility of people or readiness to change their place of residence, etc.

The significance of the social component is very important, since it is all-pervasive, influencing both other components of the macroenvironment and the internal environment of the organization. Social processes change relatively slowly. However, if certain social changes occur, they lead to many very significant changes in the organization's environment. Therefore, the organization must seriously monitor possible social changes. Analysis of the technological component allows you to promptly see the opportunities that the development of science and technology opens up for the production of new products, for the improvement of existing products and for the modernization of manufacturing technology and sales of products. The progress of science and technology brings with it enormous opportunities and no less enormous threats to firms. Many organizations are unable to see the new prospects that are opening up, since the technical capabilities for implementing fundamental changes are mainly created outside the industry in which they operate. By being late with modernization, they lose their market share, which can lead to extremely negative consequences for them. When studying the various components of the macroenvironment, it is very important to keep in mind the following two points.

Firstly, all components of the macroenvironment are in a state of strong mutual influence. Changes in one of the components necessarily lead to changes in other components of the macroenvironment. Therefore, their study and analysis should be carried out not separately, but systematically, tracking not only the changes in a separate component, but also understanding how these changes will affect other components of the macroenvironment. Secondly, the degree of influence of individual components of the macroenvironment on different organizations is different. In particular, the degree of influence is manifested differently depending on the size of the organization, its industry affiliation, territorial location, etc. For example, it is believed that large organizations are more dependent on the macroenvironment than small ones.

To take this into account when studying the macroenvironment, the organization must determine for itself which of the external factors related to each of the components of the macroenvironment have a significant impact on its activities. In addition, the organization must compile a list of those external factors that are potential carriers of threats to the organization. It is also necessary to have a list of those external factors, changes in which can open up additional opportunities for the organization [2].

In order for the organization to be able to effectively study the state of the macroenvironment components, a special system for monitoring the external environment must be created. This system must carry out both special observations related to some special events, and regular (usually once a year) observations of the state of external factors important for the organization. Observations can be carried out in many different ways. The most common methods of observation are:

- analysis of materials published in books, magazines and other information publications;
- participation in professional conferences;
- analysis of the experience of the organization's activities;
- study of the opinions of the organization's employees;
- holding internal meetings and discussions.

The study of the macroenvironment components should not end with just stating what state they were in before or what state they are in now. It is also necessary to identify the trends that are characteristic of changes in the state of individual important factors and to try to predict the direction of development of these factors in order to foresee what threats the organization may face and what opportunities may open up for it in the future.

The system of macroenvironment analysis provides the necessary effect if it is supported by the top management and provides it with the necessary information, if it is closely connected with the planning system in the organization and, finally, if the work of analysts working in this system is combined with the work of specialists in strategic issues who are able to trace the connection between the data on the state of the macroenvironment and the strategic objectives of the organization and evaluate this information in terms of threats and additional opportunities for implementing the organization's strategy.

The study of the immediate environment of the organization is aimed at analyzing the state of those components of the external environment with which the organization is in direct interaction. It is important to emphasize that the organization can have a significant impact on the nature and content of this interaction, thereby it can actively participate in the formation of additional opportunities and the prevention of threats to its further existence.

The analysis of buyers as a component of the immediate environment of the organization primarily has as its task the creation of a profile of those who buy the product sold by the organization. Studying customers allows an organization to better understand what product will be accepted by customers to the greatest extent, what sales volume the organization can expect, to what extent customers are committed to the product of this particular organization, to what extent the circle of potential customers can be expanded, what awaits the product in the future, and much more.

A customer profile can be compiled based on the following characteristics:

- geographic location of the customer;
- demographic characteristics of the customer, such as age, education, field of activity, etc.;
- socio-psychological characteristics of the customer, reflecting his position in society, behavior style, tastes, habits, etc.;
- the customer's attitude to the product, reflecting why he buys this product, whether he himself is a user of the product, how he evaluates the product, etc.

By studying the buyer, the company also finds out how strong his position is in relation to it in the bargaining process. If, for example, the buyer has a limited opportunity to choose the seller of the goods he needs, then his bargaining power is significantly weakened. If, on the contrary, the seller must look for a replacement for this buyer with another one who would have less opportunity to choose the seller.

The bargaining power of the buyer also depends, for example, on how important the quality of the purchased product is for him. There are a number of factors that determine the bargaining power of the buyer, which must be revealed and studied during the analysis of the buyer. Such factors include the following:

- the ratio of the degree of dependence of the buyer on the seller to the degree of dependence of the seller on the buyer;
- the volume of purchases made by the buyer;
- the level of information of the buyer;
- the availability of substitute products;
- the cost for the buyer to switch to another seller;
- the buyer's sensitivity to price, depending on the total cost of their purchases, their focus on a certain brand, the presence of certain requirements for the quality of the product, its profit, the incentive system and responsibility of those making the purchase decision.

Supplier analysis is aimed at identifying those aspects in the activities of entities supplying the organization with various raw materials, semi-finished products, energy and information resources, finances, etc., on which the efficiency of the organization depends. Cost price and quality of the product manufactured by the organization.

Suppliers of materials and components, if they have great power, can make the organization very dependent on themselves. Therefore, when choosing suppliers, it is very important to deeply and comprehensively study their activities and their potential in order to be able to build such relationships with them that would provide the organization with maximum strength in interaction with suppliers. The competitive strength of a supplier is determined by the following factors:

- the level of supplier specialization;
- the value of the cost of switching for the supplier to other customers;
- the degree of specialization of the buyer in the acquisition of certain resources;
- the supplier's focus on working with specific customers;
- the importance of sales volume for the supplier.

When studying seeders of materials and components, first of all, you should pay attention to the following characteristics of their activities:

- the cost of the supplied goods;
- the guarantee of the quality of the supplied goods;
- the time schedule for the delivery of goods;
- punctuality and mandatory fulfillment of the terms of delivery of goods.

The study of competitors, i.e. those with whom the organization has to compete for the resources that it seeks to obtain from the external environment in order to ensure its existence, occupies a special and very important place in strategic management. This study is aimed at identifying the strengths and weaknesses of competitors and, on this basis, building its own strategy of competitive struggle.

The competitive environment is formed not only by intra-industry competitors producing similar products and selling them on the same market. The subjects of the competitive environment are also those firms that can enter the market, as well as those firms that produce a substitute product. In addition to them, the competitive environment of an organization is noticeably influenced by its customers and suppliers, who, having bargaining power, can significantly weaken the position of the organization in the competitive field. Many firms do not pay due attention to the possible threat from "aliens" and therefore lose in the competitive struggle to those who have just entered their market. It is very important to remember this and create barriers in advance on the way of entry of potential "aliens". Such barriers can be deep specialization in the production of a product, low costs due to savings from large volumes of production, control over distribution channels, the use of local features that provide an advantage in competition, etc. However, any of these measures is effective only when it is a real barrier to the "aliens".

Therefore, it is very important to be well aware of what barriers can stop or prevent a potential “alien” from entering the market, and to erect precisely these barriers.

Producers of substitute products have very highly competitive power. The peculiarity of market transformation in the case of the emergence of a substitute product is that if it has “killed” the market of the old product, it usually cannot be restored. Therefore, in order to be able to adequately meet the challenge from firms producing a substitute product, the organization must have sufficient potential to move on to creating a new type of product [3].

The analysis of the labor market is aimed at identifying its potential in providing the organization with the personnel necessary to solve its problems. The organization must study the labor market both from the point of view of the availability of personnel of the necessary specialty and qualifications, the necessary level of education, the necessary age, gender, etc., and from the point of view of the cost of labor. An important area of the study of the labor market is the analysis of the policy of trade unions that have influence on this market, since in some cases they can greatly limit access to the labor force necessary for the organization.

3.2. Analysis of the internal environment.

The internal environment of the organization is that part of the general environment that is within the organization. It has a constant and most direct impact on the functioning of the organization. The internal environment has several sections, each of which includes a set of key processes and elements of the organization, the state of which in total determines the potential and opportunities that the organization has. The personnel section of the internal environment covers such processes as: interaction between managers and workers; hiring, training and promotion of personnel; evaluation of labor results and incentives; creation and maintenance of relationships between employees, etc.

The organizational section includes: communication processes; organizational structures; norms, rules, procedures; distribution of rights and responsibilities; hierarchy of subordination. The production section includes product manufacturing, supply and warehouse management; maintenance of the technology park; implementation of research and development. The marketing section of the internal environment of the organization covers all those processes that are related to the sale of products. This is a product strategy, pricing strategy; strategy for promoting a product on the market; selection of sales markets and distribution systems. The financial section includes processes related to ensuring the efficient use and movement of the organization's funds. In particular, this is maintaining liquidity and profitability, creating investment opportunities, etc.

The internal environment is completely permeated by organizational culture, which, like the above-mentioned sections, should be subject to the most serious study in the process of analyzing the internal environment of the organization. Organizational culture can contribute to the organization being a strong, sustainably surviving structure in the competitive struggle. But it may also be that organizational culture weakens the organization, preventing it from developing successfully even if it has high technical, technological and financial potential. The particular importance of analyzing the organizational structure for strategic management is that it not only determines the relationships between people in the organization, but also has a strong influence on how the organization builds its interaction with the external environment, how it treats its clients and what methods it chooses to conduct competitive struggle.

Since organizational culture does not have a clearly expressed manifestation, it is difficult to study. However, there are nevertheless several stable points that are important to clarify in order to try to point out the weaknesses and strengths that organizational culture gives to the organization. Information about organizational culture can be obtained from various publications in which the organization presents itself. Organizations with a strong organizational culture are characterized by emphasizing the importance of people working in it. Such organizations pay great attention to explaining their corporate philosophy and promoting their values in their publications, while organizations with a weak organizational culture tend to talk about formal organizational and quantitative aspects of their activities in their publications.

An idea of organizational culture is given by observing how employees work at their workplaces, how they communicate with each other, what they prefer in conversations. Also, an understanding of organizational culture can be improved if you become familiar with how the career system is built in the organization and what criteria are used to promote employees. If employees are promoted quickly and based on individual achievements, it can be assumed that there is a weak organizational culture. If the career of employees is long-term and preference for promotion is given to the ability to work well in a team, then such an organization has clear signs of a strong organizational culture.

Understanding organizational culture is facilitated by studying whether the organization has stable commandments, unwritten norms of behavior, rituals, legends, heroes, etc., how much all employees of the organization are aware of this and how seriously they treat all this. If employees are well aware of the history of the organization, seriously and respectfully treat the rules, rituals and organizational symbols, then it can be assumed with a high degree of correspondence to reality that the organization has a strong organizational culture. In order to successfully survive in the long term, the organization must be able to predict what difficulties may arise on its path in the future, and what new opportunities may open up for it.

Therefore, strategic management, studying the external environment, focuses on identifying what threats and what opportunities the external environment conceals. In order to successfully cope with threats and effectively use opportunities, it is by no means enough to just know about them. You can know about a threat, but not be able to resist it and thus suffer a defeat. It is also possible to know about new opportunities that are opening up, but not have the potential to use them and, therefore, not be able to use them. The strengths and weaknesses of the internal environment of an organization, as well as threats and opportunities, determine the conditions for the successful existence of an organization.

Therefore, when analyzing the internal environment, strategic management is interested in identifying exactly what strengths and weaknesses the individual components of the organization and the organization as a whole have. Summarizing the above, it can be stated that the analysis of the environment, as it is carried out in strategic management, is aimed at identifying threats and opportunities that may arise in the external environment in relation to the organization, as well as the strengths and weaknesses that the organization has. It is for solving this problem that certain techniques for analyzing the environment have been developed, which are used in strategic management.

The SWOT method (the abbreviation is made up of the first letters of the English words: strength, weakness, opportunities and threats) used for environmental analysis is a fairly widely recognized approach that allows for a joint study of the external and internal environment. Using the SWOT method, it is possible to establish lines of communication between the strength and weakness inherent in the organization and external threats and opportunities. The SWOT methodology first involves identifying strengths and weaknesses, as well as threats and opportunities, and then establishing chains of connections between them, which can then be used to formulate the organization's strategy.

First, taking into account the specific situation in which the organization finds itself, a list of its weaknesses and strengths is compiled, as well as a list of threats and opportunities. After a specific list of the organization's weaknesses and strengths, as well as threats and opportunities, is compiled, the stage of establishing connections between them begins. To establish these connections, a SWOT matrix is compiled, which has the following form (see Fig. 2). On the left, two sections are allocated (strengths, weaknesses), in which all the strengths and weaknesses of the organization identified at the first stage of the analysis are entered. In the upper part of the matrix, two sections are also allocated (opportunities and threats), in which all the identified opportunities and threats are entered. At the intersection of the sections, four fields are formed: the "SIV" field (strength and opportunities); the "SIU" field (strength and threats); the "SLV" field (weakness and opportunities) and the "SLU" field (weakness and threats).

In each of these fields, the researcher must consider all possible pair combinations and select those that should be taken into account when developing a strategy for the organization's behavior. With respect to those pairs that were selected from the "SIV" field, a strategy should be developed to use the strengths of the organization in order to get a return on the opportunities that have appeared in the external environment; for those pairs that ended up in the "SLV" field, the strategy should be built in such a way as to try to overcome the weaknesses in the organization due to the opportunities that have appeared. If the pair is on the "SIU" field, then the strategy should involve using the organization's strength to eliminate threats; finally, for pairs on the "SLU" field, the organization should develop a strategy that would allow it to both get rid of weakness and try to prevent the threat looming over it.

IV. Conclusion.

As can be seen from this work, environmental analysis is a very important for developing an organization's strategy and a very complex process that requires careful monitoring of the processes occurring in the environment, assessing factors and adopting the relationship between factors and those strengths and weaknesses, as well as opportunities and threats that are contained in the external environment. It is obvious that without knowing the environment, the organization cannot exist. However, it does not float in the environment like a boat without a rudder, oars or sails. The organization studies the environment to ensure successful progress towards its goals.

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